

Environment legislation in India

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Abstract:

India is a legislation rich country with reference to pollution. Eleven major laws exist to control pollution in India and many forums for their implementation in various ways. Under these laws, provisions are made to protect the environment from all kinds of pollution related to industrial and agricultural activities. The Punjab Pollution Control Board (PPCB) is entrusted with the functions of planning a comprehensive program for the prevention, control and abatement of pollution in Punjab. PPCB has to support and encourage developments in the field of pollution control. PPCB has taken various measures to limit the amount of industrial pollution in the state but not much has been done to address agricultural pollution ([http:// www. ppcb. gov. in/ index. aspx](http://www.ppcb.gov.in/index.aspx)).

Introduction

Environmental law is an integral part of any government agency. It includes a series of laws and regulations related to water quality, air quality, and other environmental aspects. The success of environmental legislation mainly depends on how they are implemented. Legislation is also a valuable tool to educate people about their responsibility to maintain a healthy environment. Environmental law in India is based on principles of environmental law and focuses on the management of certain natural resources such as minerals, forests, and fisheries. Environmental law in India directly reflects the provisions of the Constitution. The need to protect and maintain the environment and make sustainable use of natural resources is reflected in India's constitutional framework and India's international obligations.

However, after so many initiatives in the field of environmental law to set up sustainability, India's growing economy still lacks to deal with environmental issues. Moreover, Indian regulators are trying to revise its existing environmental rules and acts, which may result in more stringent company requirements. But, these initiatives will not work if we as a society don't focus on them. People's awareness plays a significant role in such policy development, which is why we need to come together to work on these major issues. Government and non-government organisations need to work together to solve environmental issues, and there should be a stricter policy regarding environmental legislation.

What is environmental legislation

Environmental legislation is a collection of laws and regulations related to water quality, air quality, endangered wildlife, and several other environmental factors. Environmental legislation covers many laws and regulations, but they all work towards a common goal of regulating human-nature interactions to reduce threats to the environment and improve public health. As we can imagine, environmental legislation is broad, mainly because the natural environment encompasses several aspects. All this means that environmental law must take into account everything from the air we breathe, to the natural resources we depend on, to the flora and fauna that share this world with us.

After so much interconnection with each other, it becomes important for us to understand environmental legislation because we all share the same resources.

Climate change in India

If we take the example of India, then it is one of the countries most affected by climate change. About half of India's population depends on agriculture or other climate-sensitive sectors. About 12% of India is prone to floods and 16% to droughts. India is now the world's third-largest emitter of greenhouse gases after China and the United States. From 1990 to 2009, India's annual emissions nearly tripled, from less than 600 tons to more than 1,700 tons. From 2008 to 2035, India's annual carbon emissions are expected to increase nearly 2.5 times. Net greenhouse gas emissions from India's land use, change, and forestry in 2007 was 1,727.71 million tons of carbon dioxide. While the energy sector accounts for 8% of net CO₂ emissions, the industrial sector, agriculture, and waste sectors account for 22%, 17%, and 3% of net CO₂ emissions, respectively. As a result, climate change and energy are now the focus of local, state, and national concerns around the world. While India has previously emphasised that it is a developing country with historically low per capita emissions rates and is not responsible for past greenhouse gas emissions, India has now become a key player in international negotiations. It has begun implementing a diverse set of laws, improving energy efficiency, developing clean energy and preparing for the impacts of climate change nationally and individually.

On the other hand, India is considered to be a land of spirituality and philosophy and is also the land of rivers as it has 14 major rivers, 44 medium rivers, and 55 minor rivers. From the Ganges in the north to Kaveri in the south, the waterways are considered sacred by most devout Hindu pilgrims, as religious texts say the Ganges can purify the sins of the bathers. It is said that the sight of Narmada is enough to purify the waters. However, India's rivers are increasingly becoming dumping grounds for domestic, industrial, and agricultural waste. A polluted environment threatens human existence on earth, thereby endangering human beings. A country's borders cannot limit these environmental issues to a specific country or region, but their impact is global. This massive environmental degradation has drawn global attention to protecting and preserving the earth's environment.

Therefore, efforts are being made to inculcate environmental awareness among the masses. Education makes people more aware of the environment and environmental issues. Existing policies, laws, precedents, regulations, norms, decisions, etc., already constitute a large and complicated apparatus of documents and powers conferred on specific institutions or persons. However, the current laws also seem unable to solve the problem and that more may be needed, the question inevitably arises as to how much resources, wealth, energy, and intelligence India should devote to this regulation and control task.

Need for environment legislation

The genesis of various national legislations lies in environmental issues. There should be effective legislation to protect the environment; otherwise, the growing population will create havoc and will destroy the environment. Another important aspect is the enforcement of these laws. We must vigorously and effectively enforce the law to protect our environment from further degradation and pollution. Pollution is an important factor, ignoring political territory and legislative jurisdiction. Therefore, environmental problems are global in nature. To prevent such problems, it is not only necessary to enact environmental laws at the national level but also the international level.

While modern society is increasingly concerned about global environmental issues, developing countries also have their complex, severe, and rapidly growing pollution problems. The potent combination of industrialization development and mass consumption trends is exacerbated by foreign companies operating with little regard for the impact on the local environment. Pollution is not just a health issue; it is a broader social issue, as pollution has the potential to destroy families and communities. Pollution issues are also closely related to the mode of development in developing countries. Nonetheless, many developing countries either do not have pollution control policies or do not have sufficient enforcement structures to ensure that policies are effective.

The combination of rapid industrial development (especially petrochemical and heavy industry), strong economic growth, and unprecedented urban expansion have substantially increased pollutant emissions.

Purpose of environment legislation

The importance of environmental legislation is that environmental protection cannot be achieved without appropriate regulations and laws. Raising environmental awareness and promoting environmental education are the means by which people do not destroy the environment but protect it for the future. However, it is the legislation that ensures that environmental protection is actually implemented in everyday life. Legislation requires businesses, companies, the public, industries, etc., to protect the environment and prevent environmental degradation. It provides severe penalties for those who do not abide by the laws and rules. Ultimately, this type of enforcement ensures that ideas and plans are turned into practical efforts to protect the environment. At the international level, several environmental treaties and conventions attempt to address environmental issues. With the Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment (1972), the United Nations began to emphasize environmental aspects. Since then, several nations have adopted seventy international treaties, declarations, charters, agreements, and so on. These efforts were made to safeguard the environment and balance human development with environmental conservation.

Laws related to environment in India

At the national level, some remarkable efforts have been made to improve and protect the environment by incorporating Amendments into the Indian Constitution. Our Constitution initially did not directly provide for the protection of the natural environment. However, following the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm in 1972, the Indian Constitution was amended to include environmental protection as a constitutional mandate. The 42nd Amendment clause (g) of Article 51A of the Constitution of India states that protecting and improving the natural environment is a fundamental duty. Every citizen of India has a duty to protect and improve the natural environment, including lakes, forests, wildlife, and rivers, and to be sympathetic to living things. A policy or directive is empowering the state as one of the Directive Principles of State Policy sets out to protect and improve the environment.

Article 48A stipulates: The state strives to protect and improve the environment and secure the country's forests and wild animals. The Ministry of Environment was established in India in 1980 to ensure a healthy environment in the country. Later, this became the Ministry of Environment and

Forests in 1985. The Ministry has overall responsibility for the management and enforcement of environmental legislation and policies. Constitutional provisions are backed by a series of laws – Acts and Rules. Most of our environmental laws are Acts of Parliament or State Legislatures. These Acts generally give regulators the power to make regulations to enforce them. The Environmental Protection Act (EPA) of 1986 came into effect shortly after the Bhopal Gas tragedy and is considered protective legislation because it filled many gaps in existing legislation.

Since then, a significant number of environmental law has been enacted to deal with specific environmental issues. In Delhi, for example, CNG was recently mandated for public transport vehicles. This reduces air pollution in Delhi.

Environment laws in India

There are so many environmental laws in force in India, and some are as follows: –

- **The Public Liability Insurance Act and Rules 1991 and Amendment, 1992**
- **The National Environmental Tribunal Act, 1995, Amendment, 2010**
- **The National Environment Appellate Authority Act, 1997**
- **The Biomedical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 1998**
- **The Environment (Siting for Industrial Projects) Rules, 1999**
- **The Municipal Solid Wastes (Management and Handling) Rules, 2000**
- **The Batteries (Management and Handling) Rules, 2001**
- **The Noise Pollution (Regulation and Control) (Amendment) Rules, 2010**
- **The Air (prevention and control of pollution) Act, 1981**
- **Scheduled Tribes and Other Traditional Forest Dwellers (Recognition of Forest Rights) Act, 2006 (FRA)**
- **The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980**

- **The Wildlife Protection Act, 1972**

- **The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974**

- **The Ozone-Depleting Substances (Regulation And Control) Rules, 2000**

- **Coastal Regulation Zone Notification, 2018**

- **The Energy Conservation Act, 2001**
- **The Energy Conservation Act, 2001 was ratified as a step toward revamping energy efficiency and**

- **The Biological Diversity Act, 2002**

- **The National Green Tribunal Act, 2010**

- **The Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972**

- **The Wildlife (Protection) Amendment Bill, 2021**

Landmark cases on environment legislation in India

J.C. Galstaun v. Dunia Lal Seal (1905)

This is the first environmental pollution incident reported in India. In this case, the plaintiff sued the defendant's adjacent factory for discharging waste liquid from its manufacturing process into a municipal drain that passed through the plaintiff's garden. He claimed that the liquid had an unpleasant smell and was harmful to the health of nearby residents, especially his own, and secondly, it damaged his health, comfort, and the market value of his garden property. The defendant admitted to foul-smelling his liquid waste but denied that it was harmful or would damage the plaintiff's property. He said his factory was licensed by the government and produced legally. The judgment was later appealed to the Calcutta High Court.

The High Court rejected the above argument and came to the conclusion that the defendant is accountable for such harm and had no such right to discharge any kind of liquid into the municipal drain. Due to such actions, the damage has actually been caused to the plaintiff. Therefore, he is entitled to substantial damages.

Rural Litigation And Entitlement Kendra, Dehradun v. State of U.P. & Ors. (1985)

In this case, the plaintiff NGO wrote a letter to the SC stating that illegal limestone mining in the Mussoorie-Dehradun area is destroying the region's fragile ecosystem. The Court treated the letter as a writ petition and heard the parties.

The Court issued a detailed Order giving various directions, noting that the reasons for the order would be set out in subsequent judgments. The Court stressed that industrial development is a necessary condition for the country's economic growth. However, when people try to achieve industrial growth through random and reckless mine operations, resulting in loss of property, loss of life, loss of basic infrastructure such as water supply, and the creation of ecological imbalances, there may ultimately be no real economic growth and no real prosperity. It was important to find an appropriate balance. When giving leases, authorities must consider all these facts and provide adequate safeguards.

M.C. Mehta & Another vs. Union of India & Others & Shriram Foods & Fertilizer Industries & Another v. Union of India & Others (1987)

M.C. Mehta filed a writ petition under Articles 21 and 32 of the Constitution. He demanded the closure of Shriram Food and Fertilizer as it manufactures hazardous substances and is located in the densely populated area of Kirti Nagar. While the petition was pending, there was a leakage of oleum gas from one of its units, which killed many people, thus, affecting the health of several others. The incident occurred a few months before the Environment (Protection) Act came into force and became the driving force behind such an effective law.

In the Judgment, Chief Justice Bhagwati mentioned that all these chemical industries are dangerous, but they cannot be removed from the country because they improve the quality of life. As dangerous as these industries are, they need to be set up as they provide many supplies, as in this case the factories supply chlorine gas to the Delhi Water Company to maintain clean drinking water. These industries are important for the country's economic growth. The case is a landmark verdict as it is the first time in Indian history that a company is liable for damages. The Supreme Court defended the environment and public rights in this case because it considered legal and social and economic factors.

M.C. Mehta v. Union of India (1997)

The Taj Mahal case, commonly known as the Taj Trapezium case, was fought by M.C. Mehta and the Union of India. In 1984, Mehta visited the Taj Mahal and noticed that the white marble of the Taj Mahal was turning yellow. To find out, he filed a petition in the Supreme Court. The petitioner stated that pollution is the main cause of the Taj Mahal's white marble turning yellow. Emissions of harmful gases such as sulfur dioxide and oxygen become acid rain. The rain damaged the monument and turned the marble yellow. Therefore, the petitioner requested the protection of the monument. The Supreme Court found that, in addition to chemicals, socioeconomic factors also affected the mining of the Taj Mahal. People living in trapeze zones are at risk of air pollution. Court ordered that 292 industries operate on safer fuels like propane instead of coke/coal; otherwise, they would have to relocate.

The Gas Authority of India Limited was in charge of applications of gas. The Court also granted certain fundamental rights to industry workers and demanded payment of their wages during relocation.

M.C. Mehta v. Union of India (1988)

In the case of *M.C. Mehta v. Union of India* (1988), a writ petition had been filed in the Supreme Court to prevent leather tanneries from dumping household and industrial waste in the river Ganga. He asked the court to stop sewage discharge into the river until a certain treatment plan has been incorporated to curb water pollution.

The Court held that polluted water can cause various water-borne diseases and is extremely harmful to the public. As for whose responsibility, the Court ruled that it was the industry's responsibility to ensure the waste was properly handled and subsequently released. Mahapalika was also held accountable for failing to perform its duties and for failing to act to prevent water pollution, according to the Court. It ordered Mahapalika to take immediate action in this regard.

The Court also ordered the federal government to make publications freely available to the general public to raise awareness of environmental issues. It went on to say that the decision will apply to all Mahaparikas who have jurisdiction over the Ganga.

The decision is still considered one of the most important in our country's environmental law. The decision involves some new scenarios and interpretations of legislation and fundamental rights.

Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar (1991)

In the case of *Subhash Kumar v. State of Bihar* (1991), petitioners had filed a public interest lawsuit against two steel companies, alleging that they dumped plant waste into the nearby Bokaro River, posing a health risk to the public. The petitioner also claimed that the State Environmental Protection Agency did not take appropriate measures to prevent such pollution. As part of their lawsuit, they asked the Court to bring legal action against the company under the Water (Pollution Prevention and Control) Act 1974 and sought permission to self-assess waste in the form of sludge and manure collected as interim relief. The State Pollution and Control Board claimed that it adequately monitored the quality of sewage entering the river; the defendant companies claimed they followed the Board's instructions concerning the prevention of pollution.

The Court found that the Board had taken effective steps to prevent the waste discharge from the factories into the river and dismissed the lawsuit. In addition, it has been determined that the petition does not qualify as a public interest lawsuit because of the petitioner's interest in obtaining larger quantities of waste in the form of slurry from one of the defendant companies from which he began to purchase slurry several years prior to the petition.

M.C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath & Ors. (1996)

In the case of *M.C. Mehta v. Kamal Nath & Ors.* (1996), the issue started when the Indian Express published an article reporting that a private company- Span Motels Private Ltd., had launched a project called Span Club. The article caught the attention of the Supreme Court. The company owner had direct contact with the family of former Minister of Environment and Forests, Kamal Nath. By the time Kamal Nath was a minister in 1994, Span Motels had occupied 27.12 acres of land, including forest land. The motel used bulldozers to change the course of the river Beas and divert the river's flow. The river was diverted to protect the motel from future flooding. The question raised was whether the construction activities carried out by the motel company were reasonable.

However, the Supreme Court ruled that the state's forest lands leased to the motel were on the banks of river Beas. The area is ecologically fragile and should not be turned into private property. This case applies the principle of public trust, which stipulates that the public cannot use rivers, coasts, forests, air, and other properties. The motel was ordered to pay damages and erect a wall no more than 4 metres apart. The Court also banned the motel from discharging untreated effluent into the river and asked the HP Pollution Commission to keep a check on it.

Samir Mehta v. Union of India (2017)

In the case of *Samir Mehta v. Union of India* (2017), an environmentalist filed a claim for damages from the sinking of a ship named M.V. Rak, carrying large quantities of coal, fuel oil, and diesel. When the ship sank on Mumbai's southern coast, a thick layer of oil formed on the sea surface, causing major damage to mangroves and marine ecosystems.

The Court ruled that the sinking of the ship was due to the negligence of the defendants and ordered defendants number 5, 7, and 11 to pay Rs 100 crores to the Ministry of Shipping, Government of India (GOI), which is till now one of the largest sums paid by a private entity for environmental damage caused.

It remains the largest compensation payment to the government by a private entity.

A global perspective on environment laws

United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, Stockholm, 1972

The United Nations Conference on the Environment, held in Stockholm in 1972, was the first world conference to focus on environmental issues. Participants adopted many principles for sound environmental management, including the Stockholm Declaration and the Action Plan for the Human Environment, as well as various resolutions. The Stockholm Declaration, containing 26 principles, brought environmental issues to the forefront of international attention, marking the beginning of a dialogue between developed and developing countries about the links between economic growth, air, water, and ocean pollution, and the well-being of people across the world.

World Conservation Strategy: Living Resource Conservation for Sustainable Development, 1980

The World Conservation Strategy, 1980 was the first international document on the conservation of biological resources developed with the participation of governments, NGOs, and other experts. The Report argues that for the development of sustainability, it should support rather than hinder conservation. Its underlying principles are the conservation of ecological processes and life support systems, the conservation of genetic diversity, and the sustainable use of species and ecosystems, and are aimed at political decision-makers, conservationists, and development practitioners. It highlights priority conservation issues and ways to address them to achieve this strategic objective.

Brundtland Report, Our Common Future, 1987

The Brundtland Report stated that serious global environmental problems are mainly caused by extreme poverty in the South and unsustainable consumption and production patterns in the North. It called for a strategy that integrates development and the environment. The main focus of the report is on sustainable development. It defines sustainable development as meeting the present's needs without compromising future generations' ability to meet their own needs. In 1989, the report was debated at the United Nations General Assembly, which decided to organize a United Nations Conference on Environment and Development.

United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), The Earth Summit, Rio de Janeiro, 1992

The Rio de Janeiro conference emphasizes how different social, economic, and environmental factors are interdependent and co-evolving and how success in one sector requires actions in other sectors to be sustained over the period. The main goal of the Rio Earth Summit is to develop a broad agenda and a new blueprint for international action on environment and development issues that would help cicerone international cooperation and development policy in the 21st century.

Earth Summit +5, United Nations General Assembly, New York, 1997

The Commission Sustainable Development (CSD) was established to monitor and report on the implementation of the Earth Summit Agreement and agreed to a five-year review of Earth Summit progress at the 1997 UN special session. This special session of the UN General Assembly assessed the responses of countries, international organizations, and sectors of civil society to the Earth Summit challenge.

World Summit on Sustainable Development, Johannesburg, 2002

The World Summit on Sustainable Development, held in Johannesburg in 2002, adopted a Political Declaration and Implementation Plan that contained provisions for various activities and measures to achieve development that respects the environment. The Summit was attended by more than 100 heads of state and government, as well as tens of thousands of government representatives and NGOs. After several days of deliberation, decisions were made on issues such as water, energy, sanitation, agriculture, and biodiversity

Conclusion

In India, the disquiet for environmental protection has not only risen to become the country's fundamental law but is also linked to the human rights policy, and it is now widely believed that the basic human right of everyone is to live in a pollution-free environment. A friendly environment is full of human dignity. It is time for the public, the public institutions, states, and Central Government to recognize the damage our development process is doing to the environment. Strict enforcement is also required. Laws are a powerful medium for enforcing citizens to observe cleanliness and thus fight pollution. Environmental protection laws in India need to be repositioned in a modern context.

However, it is important to understand that such enactment is not enough until a positive attitude on the part of everyone in society will be seen.

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